

COLLABORATION *with detectorists* in the Netherlands

ANTON CRUYSHEER &
ALEXANDER VAN DE BUNT

On September 12, 2020, a special experiment took place in the province of Utrecht (the Netherlands). For the first time in history, a day took place in which archaeologists and detectorists worked together and where finders themselves entered their own finds into the national system for archaeological finds: PAN (Portable Antiquities of the Netherlands). Here is a short report, and we hope that this day will be followed in the rest of the Netherlands and in other countries!

Metal detection is officially permitted in the Netherlands, provided that finds are reported. Landscape Heritage Utrecht is a partner organisation of the province of Utrecht and charged with carrying out the statutory task of registering private archaeological finds. Because the capacity and finance limited for this task (given the large number of discoveries made by detectorists in particular), we have worked on how to increase our effectiveness.

The answer was simple: more collaboration with detectorists, by helping and supporting them to enter their finds themselves. However, it's easier said than done, because there's quite a bit involved: identification, photography, location determination on a map in the PAN system and registration of the find – including specifications such as dimensions and weight. Understandably many finders need assistance with this.

A qualitative find registration requires mutual trust

Every detectorist knows, that there is a legal obligation to report finds. But a general report of your find without any features and good photos still doesn't say enough about the coin or artefact. If you want a qualitative find notification and registration, then cooperation will have to be sought between the registrator/recorder of archaeological finds and the detectorist. As a finds recorder, we therefore appealed to the finder's willingness to invest time and share knowledge. This is based on building mutual trust but we can also do this by also giving something back to the finder. Firstly, the appreciation and secondly it can also be the background and context of the archaeological find.

The experiment

We were looking for a way to bring the different parties together and to ensure that we work together better and more efficiently, so that we can properly map out the past. The PAN event, the very first in this form, was a pilot for this purpose. If all participants are enthusiastic, it will be an event that we will repeat annually and also want to take to the other provinces.

To see if and how cooperation could be established, we organised a PAN event from the Archaeology Reporting Point with the aim of: a fun day for the detectorists where we enter as many finds as possible together. We took an example from a 'Hackaton', where software is developed in a short time. But in this case, it was about the registration of archaeological finds.

Because the available time of the finders, this had to be an attractive day! We therefore focused on the finder as much as possible by:

- 1** A cool location: a water line fort (World Heritage site) at fort Vechten
- 2** An event T-shirt for each participant
- 3** For each participant a goodie bag with cool gadgets (digital coin scale, measuring tape, display cases, refreshments, etc.).
- 4** A determination team of archaeological material specialists who assisted the finders in the identification of their finds
- 5** Presence of the national association De Detector Amateur
- 6** Archaeologists from the PAN, who assisted finders with technical support for the registration, including find photography (several stations for taking good photos were set up)
- 7** A nice introductory presentation explaining the purpose and method of the day
- 8** An excellent (luxury) lunch, snacks and drinks
- 9** A (sponsored) prize package for the most special/important finds
- 10** Each winning find will get its own article on the website of UtrechtAltijd in 2021

WINNING FINDS

Here are just some of the many finds that were recorded, and some of the winning finds below!

Cushion fibula ca.800-900 AD

Another nice find that could be registered dates from the early Middle Ages and concerns a cloak pin (fibula), of the cushion fibula type. In many cases, cushion fibulae are inlaid with silver, but colored enamel (molten glass) is quite unique. Usually this has (largely) disappeared, but with this find it is still completely intact!

Bracket fibula ca.70-150 AD

This Roman fibula with hinge construction finished in second place. The bracket has a rectangular decorative surface with inscription! These types of fibulae are not especially popular in the Gallic provinces of Rome but are also found in all western provinces from Britain to the Balkans. Strange, such a small fragment in second place? That's because of the inscription. Only three of these are known in the Netherlands. The inscription reads MERI, which means 'deen'. This text is intended to be sexual and falls within the "love inscriptions" box.

Ring with sapphire ca.1250-1500 AD

This beautiful, heavy-duty medieval gold ring. The stone is a blue sapphire or lapis lazuli. This type of claw-mount ring is already known, but new to this ring are the curls (volute) on the side. The ring rises like a building, which is a typical feature of the Renaissance. The ring therefore probably dates from the 14th or 15th century.

Small coin treasure from the time of Pepin the Short (714-768)

Pepijn de Korte (dutch) was the father of Charlemagne. In 714 AD. He became court master and from 751 until his death the first king of the Franks of the Carolingian house.

Hardly any coin treasures are known from this period and that is why this find was the winner of the event (rewarded with a sponsored detector)!